

Interreg

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Alpine Space

Forest EcoValue

COMMUNICATION AND PRESS RELEASE (IN RELATION TO THE FINAL CONFERENCE)

D.3.3.4

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: LGCA (LOMBARDY GREEN
CHEMISTRY ASSOCIATION) / PP7

Interreg Alpine Space Programme 21-27

Carbon neutral and resource sensitive Alpine region

SO 2.2: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy

Forest EcoValue:

Supporting multiple forest ecosystem services through new circular/green/bio markets and value chains

Project ID: ASP0100005

List of the Forest EcoValue project partners

- PP1. Finpiemonte SpA – Regional financial and development agency / **Coordinator** [FINPIE]
- PP2. Lombardy Foundation for the Environment – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente [FLA]
- PP4. National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement [INRAE]
- PP5. Slovenia Forest Service – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije [ZGS]
- PP6. Institute for Environmental Planning and Spatial Development GmbH & Co. KG – Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG [Ifuplan]
- PP7. Lombardy Green Chemistry Association – Cluster Lombardo della Chimica Verde [LGCA]
- PP8. University of Graz, Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences [UNIGRAZ]
- PP9. Regional Centre for Forest Property Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes – Centre Régional de la Propriété Forestière [CNPF]
- PP10. The French National Forest Office – Office National des Forêts [ONF]
- PP11. Hozcluster Steiermark – Woodcluster Styria [HCS]

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Glossary

AG – Action Group (within EUSALP framework)

ASP – Alpine Space Programme

CNPF – Centre National de la Propriété Forestière

CO₂ – Carbon dioxide

EUSALP – EU Strategy for the Alpine Region

FES – Forest Ecosystem Services

FLA – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente

FINPIE – Finpiemonte SpA

HCS – Holzcluster Steiermark

IFUPLAN – Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG

INRAE – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement

LL – Living Lab

LGCA – Lombardy Green Chemistry Association

NTFPs – Non-Timber Forest Products

ONF – Office National des Forêts

PP – Project Partner

PPP – Public–Private Partnership

TG – Target Group

UNIGRAZ – University of Graz

ZGS – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije (Slovenia Forest Service)

1. Introduction

After 42 months of transnational research, co-creation, and innovation across five Alpine countries, the Forest EcoValue project — co-funded by the European Union through the Interreg Alpine Space Programme — has successfully concluded its activities. The project has delivered concrete methodologies, business models, regional roadmaps, and policy recommendations to support sustainable forest management and the development of ecosystem service markets across the Alpine region. Through a multi-actor and place-based approach, it has strengthened cooperation among public authorities, research institutions, and private stakeholders, fostering new opportunities for the valorisation of forest ecosystem services.

Ahead of the official project conclusion, scheduled for 30 April 2026, the Forest EcoValue Final Conference represented the key milestone marking the culmination of the project's activities. Held on 26 March 2026 in Turin (Italy), at the headquarters of Regione Piemonte, the event constituted the main concluding dissemination moment of the project. Held alongside the meeting of the Alpine Convention Permanent Committee meeting, it ensured high institutional visibility and direct engagement with key stakeholders at Alpine and European level.

Through this final transnational event, the consortium disseminated the project's main results beyond the Alpine Living Labs, while reinforcing dialogue at European level on forest ecosystem services and sustainable forest management. The Final Conference contributed to consolidating project achievements, enhancing their visibility, and promoting their uptake among relevant stakeholders, while supporting the integration of Forest EcoValue outcomes into future policy developments and initiatives in the Alpine region.

Building on this, the present deliverable provides an overview of the communication and press actions implemented in relation to the project closure, with a specific focus on the Final Conference. In particular, it describes the activities carried out before and after the event, highlighting their contribution to increasing visibility, fostering stakeholder engagement, and strengthening the overall dissemination of the project results.

2. Project overview

Forests of the Alpine Space play a key role in climate change mitigation and resilience, providing multiple ecosystem services (ES) and environmental and social benefits such as CO₂ absorption, air pollution reduction, biodiversity enhancement, and protection against natural hazards. However, they are threatened by abandonment, climate change, and territorial degradation, which progressively reduce natural resources and the provision of forest ES (FES). Maintenance costs of Alpine forests are high, and public funds and traditional wood value chains are insufficient to cover them. Economic valuation and payment schemes for FES are widely discussed but rarely successfully applied.

The Forest EcoValue project addresses this challenge by developing innovative, sustainable business models for forest management and maintenance, supporting new bio-based value chains and ES markets, and involving different sectors, public and private actors, and citizens. Restoring and maintaining healthy forests has been recognised as a source of value for the Alpine region, while also creating business opportunities and green jobs for Alpine communities.

The project focuses on a subset of FES from the following categories:

1. **Provisioning** (e.g. biomass, raw materials, chemicals) with a specific focus on non-timber forest products, and on the production of woody biomass for energy, integrated into circular energy markets.
2. **Regulating** (e.g. biodiversity, natural risk reduction, CO₂ absorption) concretely working on carbon and biodiversity credits, natural risk management through protective forests, and innovative environmental finance instruments such as green bonds and reverse auctions.
3. **Cultural** (e.g. recreation, habitat experience, health) particularly enhancing recreational and tourism services and spiritual and cultural services.

These services have been explored and tested within Living Labs (LLs) across five countries, located in different Alpine territories and representing diverse ecological and socio-economic contexts:

1. **Italy – Valle Tanaro, Piedmont:** The LL in Valle Tanaro explores innovative approaches to valorising chestnut groves, promoting non-timber forest products, developing carbon and biodiversity credits, and fostering experiential activities linked to forest and rural heritage.
2. **France – Haute-Savoie:** Grand Annecy and Thonon LLs focus respectively on two aspects: 1) recreational ecosystem services, enhancing the value of forests through the sale of experiences such as ecotourism, outdoor activities, and educational programmes; 2) enhancing the value of water regulation services through a public-private partnership.
3. **Slovenia – Karavanke Mountains, municipality Tržič:** The Slovenian LL addresses natural risk management with a focus on torrent control, advances solutions for wood biomass supply chains and promotes sustainable tourism and recreational use of forests.
4. **Austria – Province of Styria:** The Styrian LL concentrates on biodiversity and habitat provision and carbon sequestration and storage through innovative financing mechanisms such as reverse auctions.
5. **Germany – Tegernsee Valley, Upper Bavaria:** The German LL explores spiritual and cultural services, such as forest cemeteries with biodegradable urns, while also fostering habitat and biodiversity conservation through collaborative public-private partnerships.

Accordingly, the project is aiming to:

1. Map and analyse the Alpine Space forests delivery capacity of FES;
2. Identify and estimate the economic potential, define business models and FES market frameworks;
3. Test the models/tools developed by the consortium in pilot LLs involving local players;
4. Compare results at transnational level, identifying obstacles and facilitating factors;
5. Analyse the need for innovative policies to foster forest maintenance, FES markets, and new value chains;

6. Elaborate refined transferable tools/models and policy proposals to enable new markets and value chains and ensure the expected FES.

Throughout the project, a continuous participatory process is carried out within the Living Labs. Stakeholders' active involvement in these labs is essential for co-designing and testing models and tools, ensuring that the innovative approaches are rooted in local realities. In parallel, public events and capacity-building workshops have strengthened engagement, supported knowledge transfer, and provided regular updates on project activities. This participatory and long-term approach, tested across the five territories, is paving the way for refined, transferable tools and policy proposals that can unlock new markets and value chains while safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services in the Alpine Space.

Project duration: 42 months

Forest EcoValue Final Conference

The Forest EcoValue Final Conference, held on 26 March 2026 in Turin (Italy), at the headquarters of Regione Piemonte, represented a key transnational event, marking the culmination of the project's activities and providing a strategic platform to disseminate its main results to a broad audience of stakeholders at Alpine and European level. Held alongside the meeting of the Alpine Convention Permanent Committee meeting, the event ensured high international visibility and strong institutional engagement, reinforcing the policy relevance of the project outcomes.

Participation in the conference (64 participants) was ensured through a combination of targeted and open dissemination actions. Invitations were circulated both through direct outreach to relevant stakeholders

and through a dedicated LinkedIn communication campaign. Registrations were collected via an online registration form, allowing for an efficient organisation of participants and contributing to broadening the audience beyond the immediate project network.

The conference gathered a diverse audience including policymakers, representatives of regional and national authorities, research institutions, project partners, and stakeholders involved in forest management, ecosystem services, and sustainable value chains. The participation of representatives from the Alpine Convention and EUSALP further strengthened the link between project results and ongoing policy processes at transnational level.

Programme of the event

The agenda, visible below and published on the [project website](#), was structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the project's achievements and their practical implications.

Interreg Alpine Space Co-funded by the European Union

Forest EcoValue FINAL CONFERENCE

FOREST ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND SUSTAINABLE VALUE CHAINS IN THE ALPINE REGION

FORMAT: IN-PERSON (ONLINE PARTICIPATION POSSIBLE)

14:00 – 14:10	Welcome & institutional framing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marco Gallo, Regional Minister for Mountain and Territorial Development, Regione Piemonte, Italy
14:10 – 14:20	Forest EcoValue: project vision, challenges and approach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Susanna Longo, Finpiemonte SpA, Project Coordinator, Italy
14:20 – 14:40	Forest Ecosystem Services Assessment and Policy-Relevant Insights <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frederic Berger, INRAE, France
14:40 – 15:05	Economic Value and Business Models for Forest Ecosystem Services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Victoria Yavorskaya, University of Graz, Austria Luca Cetara, Fondazione Lombardia per l'Ambiente, Italy
15:05 – 15:25	From Living Labs to Road Maps for Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stefan Marzelli, IFUPLAN, Germany
15:25 – 15:45	Territorial Added Value: Lessons from Pilot Areas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of two territorial cases
15:45 – 16:20	Roundtable - External Perspectives From scientific approaches to practical application: Scaling Up Forest Ecosystem Services in the Alpine Region <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Speaker 1, Alpine Convention Speaker 2, Alpine Convention Speaker 3, EUSALP
16:20 - 16:30	Closing Remarks

www.alpine-space.eu/project/forest-ecovalue/ [forest-ecovalue](#)

The event opened with the institutional welcome by the Regional Minister for Mountain and Territorial Development of Regione Piemonte, complemented by a video message from the Alpine Space Project Officer, who provided greetings and expressed appreciation for the work carried out by the consortium. This introduction was followed by the presentation of the Forest EcoValue vision, key challenges, and methodological approach by the Project Coordinator.

Subsequent sessions focused on the core thematic areas of the project. Scientific insights on forest ecosystem services and their policy relevance were presented, highlighting the importance of integrating these services into decision-making processes. This was complemented by presentations on the economic valuation of forest ecosystem services and the development of innovative business models, demonstrating how environmental benefits can be translated into sustainable market opportunities.

A dedicated session illustrated how the Living Labs contributed to the co-creation and testing of solutions, leading to the development of concrete roadmaps for future implementation. In addition, territorial experiences from pilot areas were presented, showcasing the added value generated at local level and the transferability potential of the project results across the Alpine region.

The conference also featured a roundtable discussion with external stakeholders, including representatives from the Alpine Convention and EUSALP, focusing on how to scale up forest ecosystem services from scientific approaches to practical applications. This session fostered dialogue on policy integration, replication potential, and the role of transnational cooperation in supporting sustainable forest management.

The conference also generated active interaction with the audience through questions and requests for further clarification from participants. The discussion confirmed the strong interest in the project results, particularly regarding the practical applicability of the tools developed, the transferability of the Living Lab experiences, and the policy implications for Alpine territories.

The event concluded with closing remarks summarising the key messages and future perspectives, emphasising the importance of continuing collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

Communication and press activities before the Final Conference

The Final Conference was supported by a well-structured communication approach that ensured solid media visibility before, during, and after the event. Information about the conference was shared through targeted outreach activities aimed at both specialised stakeholders and a broader audience, helping to boost engagement during the registration phase and increase overall exposure.

In preparation for the Final Conference, a set of targeted communication actions was put in place to maximise visibility and encourage participation. A "Save the Date" visual was created and shared across partners' channels, highlighting the key details of the event (date, location, main focus and QRcode for registrations).

Interreg Co-funded by the European Union

Alpine Space

Forest EcoValue

This transnational cooperation project is funded by INTERREG ALPINE SPACE 2021-2027 and aims at contributing to the creation of green business models and job opportunities in the Alpine region and restoring forest.

**FOREST ECOVALUE
FINAL CONFERENCE**

**FOREST ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
AND SUSTAINABLE VALUE CHAINS
IN THE ALPINE REGION**

 **WEDNESDAY, 26 MARCH 2026
14H00-16H30**

 **GRATTACIELO PIEMONTE
TURIN, ITALY**

REGISTER HERE!

www.alpine-space.eu/project/forest-ecovalue/ forest-ecovalue

This initial communication helped raise awareness about the initiative and provided an early boost to registrations, ensuring a good level of engagement ahead of the conference.

Pre-event communication activities were also strongly supported through LinkedIn. In fact, a targeted sponsored LinkedIn campaign was activated on 19 February 2026 – and ended the day before the event - to maximise stakeholder engagement during the registration phase. The content was delivered directly to selected target audiences rather than relying solely on organic visibility. In total, 18 sponsored ads were published throughout the campaign period: 12 posts were launched in the initial phase, while an additional 6 posts were activated in the final weeks as part of a dedicated boost strategy to reinforce visibility and increase last-minute registrations.

The campaign was carefully targeted to reach key stakeholder groups relevant to the project and the event, i.e. policymakers, public authorities, regional and local administrations, forest owners and managers, enterprises, financial actors, researchers and civil society organisations.

Below are some extracts of ads used within the campaign, appeared directly in the LinkedIn feeds of the selected audience:

Forest EcoValue
 306 follower
 6 giorni • 🌐

From biophysical assessment to economic feasibility and governance tools: discover the Living Lab results, innovative economic frameworks and business model archetypes, that enhance forest ecosystem services and create sustainable value chains.
 Practical insights from Living Labs in Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia.
 📍 Turin | In-person
 Free event – Limited capacity
 Secure your seat now.

Mostra traduzione

From evidence to economic viability: Forest Ecosystem Services
 docs.google.com

Forest EcoValue
 306 follower
 6 giorni • 🌐

Are you working in sustainability, biotechnology or regional innovation? The Forest EcoValue Final Conference connects research, governance and economic innovation to strengthen Alpine forest ecosystems.
 Evidence-based results. Transferable models. Policy impact.
 📅 26 March 2026 | Turin
 Limited seats available.
 Register today.

Mostra traduzione

Research Meets Sustainable Forestry
 docs.google.com

Forest EcoValue
 306 follower
 6 giorni • 🌐

Join leading experts, policy makers and practitioners in Turin for the Forest EcoValue Final Conference.
 Discover how forest ecosystem services are being assessed, valued and translated into transnational guidelines, regional roadmaps and policy recommendations across the Alpine region.
 📍 In-person event – Palazzo della Regione Piemonte
 📌 Free participation – Limited seats
 Register now to secure your place.

Mostra traduzione

Forest EcoValue Final Conference | 26 March 2026
 docs.google.com

In parallel, a post available to the public audience was published on the project's LinkedIn page.

Forest EcoValue
 337 follower
 1m • Modificato •

SAVE THE DATE | FOREST ECOVALUE FINAL CONFERENCE
 Forest ecosystem services and sustainable value chains in the Alpine region

📅 Thursday, 26 March 2026 | 14:00–16:30 CET | Palazzo della Regione Piemonte, Turin (Italy)
 📍 In-person event (online format is available) | Free registration

🌐 The **Forest EcoValue** Final Conference marks the conclusion of the **Forest EcoValue Interreg Alpine Space** project, after four years of transnational cooperation across the **#AlpineRegion!**

It brings together policymakers, public authorities, practitioners, researchers and stakeholders to reflect on what works, what can be scaled up, and what comes next for **#ForestEcosystemServices** in the **#AlpineRegion**, showcasing consolidated, evidence-based results developed through Living Labs in Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia.

Join us to explore how **#ForestEcosystemServices** can be effectively integrated into sustainable value chains and policy frameworks.

Don't miss the opportunity to participate and discover the results achieved by the **Forest EcoValue** project!

📌 Register here: <https://lnkd.in/dH-z4eys>
 💡 Discover the agenda and further information at <https://lnkd.in/dfm7AKcM>

We look forward to welcoming you in Turin!

#ForestEcoValue #Interreg #FinalConference #FinalEvent #ForestEcosystemServices #AlpineRegion #AlpineSpace #LivingLabs

Mostra traduzione

Forest EcoValue | Final Conference
docs.google.com

A dedicated online registration link was set up and shared across all communication channels, allowing participants to easily register for the event. At the end of the registration period, a total of 73 participants were registered for the Final Conference, of which 64 were actual participants. In more detail:

- 37 participants attended in person;
- 27 participants followed the event online.

Based on the number of people registered for the event, campaign contributed significantly to reaching a geographically diverse audience and ensuring participation beyond the immediate project network.

In terms of stakeholder composition, the registrations confirm that the communication activities reached the main target groups: public authorities and policymakers (34), consultants / NGO representatives/practitioners (13), researchers and research bodies (8), enterprises, financial/professional actors and civil society representatives (8), and forest owners/managers and forestry operators (5). This composition shows a well-balanced mix of institutional, technical, scientific and market-oriented profiles, fully consistent with the multi-actor approach promoted by the project.

In addition to the official project page, the event was promoted through the channels of several project partners, including FINPIEMONTE (PP1), FLA (PP2), and SFS (PP5), as well as by external organisations active in the sector, such as ERSAF (Regional Agency for Agriculture and Forestry Services). This coordinated effort helped extend the outreach of the initiative beyond the immediate project network, engaging a broader community of stakeholders.

In parallel, several press-related actions were carried out to further promote the event. A dedicated news item was published on the project website (<https://www.alpine-space.eu/event/forest-ecovalue-showcases-final-results-at-the-final-conference/>), presenting the objectives and relevance of the Final Conference within the broader project context. In addition, Finpiemonte contributed to the dissemination effort by publishing news articles on its institutional website, available at the following links:

- <https://www.finpiemonte.it/news/forest-ecovalue-final-conference-turin>
- <https://www.finpiemonte.it/news/il-21-marzo-celebriamo-la-giornata-internazionale-delle-foreste>

These combined actions ensured consistent communication coverage in the lead-up to the event, reaching both specialised stakeholders and a wider audience, and contributing to strengthening the overall visibility of the Final Conference.

Communication and press activities after the Final Conference

Shortly after the event, a [LinkedIn post](#) published on 27 March 2026 highlighted the main outcomes, complemented by additional posts shared by project partners both ahead of and following the conference, further extending its reach across different networks.

Media coverage was also reinforced by Finpiemonte, which issued a press release (see below) and compiled a press review; these materials are accessible through the news article published on its website (<https://www.finpiemonte.it/progetti-strategici/conferenza-finale-del-progetto-il-materiale-condiviso>).

The same page also provides access to the presentations delivered during the conference, making it easier to share the project results with a wider audience beyond those who attended.

Foreste: dal Piemonte modelli europei per trasformare il valore ambientale in sviluppo

Torino, 26 marzo 2026 – Le foreste alpine possono diventare una leva concreta di sviluppo economico sostenibile, ma oggi una parte rilevante del loro valore – dalla biodiversità all'assorbimento di CO₂ fino alla protezione dai rischi naturali – non è ancora riconosciuta dal mercato.

È quanto emerge da **Forest EcoValue**, progetto europeo del Programma Interreg Alpine Space promosso dalla Regione Piemonte e coordinato da Finpiemonte, con il supporto tecnico di IPLA, che ha coinvolto partner istituzionali e scientifici di cinque Paesi alpini (Austria, Francia, Germania, Italia e Slovenia).

Nell'ambito della Presidenza italiana della Convenzione delle Alpi, durante l'83° meeting del Comitato permanente – l'organo esecutivo che riunisce gli otto Paesi alpini e l'Unione Europea impegnati nella tutela e nello sviluppo sostenibile dello spazio alpino –, in apertura della seconda giornata dei lavori, Finpiemonte ha presentato le evidenze del progetto, che sono state accolte con molto interesse e apprezzamento dalle Parti della Convenzione, inclusa l'Italia rappresentata dal Ministero dell'Ambiente. A margine del meeting, Finpiemonte e Regione Piemonte hanno promosso la Conferenza finale del progetto presso la sede regionale, presentando risultati consolidati e basati su evidenze scientifiche, sviluppati e testati attraverso i Living Lab attivati nei territori alpini dei Paesi partner. L'evento ha riunito rappresentanti della Convenzione delle Alpi ed esponenti di rilievo di enti italiani ed europei, impegnati nelle politiche e nelle iniziative per la gestione e la valorizzazione delle foreste. Nel corso dei lavori sono stati illustrati strumenti innovativi per valutare i servizi ecosistemici forestali, integrarli nelle filiere economiche e sviluppare modelli di governance e finanziamento sostenibili.

Il progetto ha lavorato su cinque territori pilota dell'arco alpino, veri e propri laboratori territoriali in cui amministrazioni pubbliche, imprese, proprietari forestali e altri stakeholder hanno contribuito a definire soluzioni concrete per la valorizzazione economica dei servizi ecosistemici.

In Piemonte, il Living Lab della Valle Tanaro ha evidenziato come la sola produzione forestale copra circa il 60% dei costi di gestione, mentre l'integrazione con mercati del carbonio e della biodiversità, attività turistiche e nuove forme di collaborazione pubblico-privata possa portare alla sostenibilità economica nel medio periodo.

Il progetto rafforza il ruolo del Piemonte nella cooperazione alpina e nei programmi europei, mettendo in relazione tutela ambientale, sviluppo economico e finanza verde. Si inserisce inoltre in un percorso già avviato dalla Regione Piemonte, che negli ultimi anni ha sviluppato strumenti pionieristici come il registro regionale dei crediti di carbonio e iniziative a sostegno della gestione forestale sostenibile e della filiera foresta-legno.

<<Il Piemonte si conferma laboratorio d'Europa per la gestione del capitale naturale. Grazie all'esperienza dei Living Lab di Forest EcoValue, abbiamo tracciato una rotta chiara: dare un valore

economico concreto a ciò che la foresta offre alla collettività. Con oltre il 37% del territorio coperto da boschi, la nostra regione vanta una delle superfici forestali più estese d'Italia: un patrimonio imprescindibile per sviluppare strumenti innovativi che integrino tutela ambientale e crescita delle valli. Parliamo di interventi che toccano la filiera del legno, la tutela della biodiversità, il turismo esperienziale e i crediti di carbonio. Il nostro impegno come Regione è fornire alle realtà montane strumenti normativi e finanziari all'avanguardia, come il Cluster Legno, per favorire la collaborazione tra imprese, ricerca e istituzioni. Proteggere la montagna, oggi, significa trasformare l'innovazione ambientale in occupazione e futuro per chi la vive»>> ha dichiarato l'Assessore regionale allo sviluppo montano, aree interne, foreste, attività minerarie, pianificazione paesaggistica e territoriale, aree protette e biodiversità, Marco Gallo.

<<Siamo affezionati al concetto di Valore in Finpiemonte perché rappresenta un cambio di paradigma nell'utilizzo delle risorse, che sposta l'attenzione dalla dimensione del volume delle risorse erogate a quella dei risultati che si producono con queste risorse, cambio fondamentale per garantire il loro utilizzo efficiente e sostenibile. Con Forest EcoValue abbiamo applicato questi metodi dimostrando con progetti pilota integrati che è possibile trasformare il valore ambientale delle foreste in opportunità concrete per i territori»>> ha dichiarato il Direttore Generale di Finpiemonte, Mario Alparone.

Tra le priorità emerse, il rafforzamento dei mercati del carbonio e della biodiversità, lo sviluppo di modelli di finanziamento pubblico-privato e la diffusione su scala più ampia delle soluzioni sperimentate nei territori alpini.

Forest EcoValue rappresenta un esempio concreto di come la cooperazione europea possa tradursi in strumenti operativi e opportunità di investimento, capaci di valorizzare il capitale naturale e sostenere lo sviluppo delle aree montane.

Finpiemonte S.p.A. - Ufficio stampa
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comunicazione@finpiemonte.it](https://www.finpiemonte.it/comunicazione@finpiemonte.it)
011/5717882 - 3355932082

Other communication activities on project conclusion

As part of the communication activities at project conclusion, additional actions were implemented to consolidate the visibility of the achieved results and ensure their wide dissemination among target audiences. In particular, a news item was published on the project website dedicated to the conclusion of the project, complemented by a LinkedIn post aimed at further increasing its outreach and engagement. The published news also served as an opportunity to promote the dissemination of the video developed within the final publication (D3.3.3), which presents the project's activities and outcomes through a visual storytelling approach, making the content more accessible and engaging for a broad and diverse audience. In the weeks following the project conclusion, project partners will also be actively involved in publishing and resharing this content through their own social media channels, further amplifying its reach and ensuring continued visibility beyond the project's lifetime.

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